

Section-3 : Materia Medica on Phyto-Homeopathy Remedies

Phyto-remedies are one of the lesser explored areas of homeopathic therapeutics. They are based on the rich medicinal characteristics of plants and the dynamic potentiation of these properties. This section discusses the multi-faceted principles, evidence-based applications and clinical significance of phyto-constituents derived medicines in contemporary homeopathy. With this view, we hope to contribute to the understanding of their modest but significant influence on the human organism.

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A Homeopathic Elucidation of *Ephedrinum muriaticum* with Clinical & Symptomatological Insights

Ephedrinum muriaticum

Ephedrinum muriaticum is a semi-synthetic alkaloid preparation corresponding to ephedrine hydrochloride, originally derived from *Ephedra vulgaris*, a plant long documented in traditional herbal medicine and utilized in homeopathic materia medica. The plant *Ephedra vulgaris* belongs to the Umbelliferae family known for their poison elements. It is believed that there is 200% increase in the amount of Ephedrine when collected in the autumn as compared in Spring.¹

History and authority

The symptoms of *Ephedrinum muriaticum*, with its proving has been documented in prominent homeopathic references such as P. N. Varma, Indu Vaid, Encyclopaedia of Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia, Updated edition 2007, B. Jain Publishers, New Delhi. Not much is available on the clinical use and symptomatology of *Ephedrinum muriaticum*. Earlier mentions of the medicine have been made in the British Pharmaceutical Codex.²

Clinically used for

It is used as a bronchodilator in cases of bronchial asthma and acute bronchospasm, helping to relieve breathing difficulties. It is also employed as a nasal decongestant in conditions of catarrh and allergic rhinitis. Additionally, it plays an important role in managing hypotension, particularly during anaesthesia, by raising blood pressure. In certain cases of cardiac weakness and circulatory collapse, it acts as a stimulant to restore proper functioning of the heart and circulation.

Prepared by

Ephedrinum muriaticum is prepared by triturating the Muriate (Hydrochloride) of Ephedrine, an alkaloid obtained from the plant *Ephedra vulgaris*, according to the methods of Homeopathic pharmacopoeia. This alkaloid called Ephedrine has been traditionally known for its established action in controlling asthma. Apart from its use in bronchial asthma it is also used as a headache reliever.³

Symptomatology:

Head

Headache.

Mouth

Feeling of eyes being pushed out.

Nose

Reduce swelling of turbinates. In Hay fever and associated symptoms.

Throat

Exophthalmic goitre.

Respiratory

Oppression of the chest with difficult breathing and asthmatic attacks, with a sensation of suffocation and tightness. Dryness of mucous membranes with nasal congestion and persistent coryza. Relieves bronchospasm and promotes freer respiration.

Circulatory

Rapid heart action with marked palpitations and a tendency to raise blood pressure. Fullness in the head, and circulatory

excitement with palpitated action of heart. Useful in hypotension during anaesthesia or collapse.

Urinary

Retention of urine and associated problems.⁴

General

Heightened activity of heart and lungs. Ill effects of anaesthesia. Circulatory collapse.

Dosage

1X and higher. Also, used externally as snuff, nasal ointment or nasal drops.²

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A Consolidated Symptomatology of Reserpinum Derived from Homeopathic Literature

Reserpine

Reserpine is a naturally occurring indole alkaloid obtained from the roots of *Rauwolfia serpentina*, a medicinal plant well documented in traditional Ayurvedic medicine and subsequently adopted into modern therapeutics and homeopathic materia medica. It is commercially also identified by the name Serpasil Ciba.

History and authority

The efficacy of Reserpine has been documented in prominent homeopathic reference O. A Julian in his *Materia Medica of New Homoeopathic Therapeutics*, further elaborating on the clinical use and symptomatology.¹ As per his records, the homeopathic proving was carried out on a group of thirteen provers during the winter of 1964-65 with the potencies 3x, 5c, 7c, 9c, 15c and 30c. But, at the same time, a psycho-pharmacodynamic experiment on animals, whose object was to research into the verification of the law of analogy and identity, made it possible along the way to note the presence of a pathogenetic symptomatology. As a result of this, and for the very first time in the history of symptomatological study, it has also been possible to describe an animal symptomatology, of the mouse and guinea pig. This proving was conducted on a batch of one hundred mice and sixty guinea-pigs, and the potencies used were 3x, 5c, 7c, 9c, 15c, 30c and placebo. The simultaneous human experiment was conducted with the same potencies, and the placebo.² A compilation of the outcomes of the symptomatological studies has been included in the elucidation below.

Clinically use

It is useful in generalised state of asthenia, hypertonia, and lack of movement. Because of its soothing effect on the neurological system, it is also used as a tranquilizer in some mental illnesses, including schizophrenia, agitation, suicidal tendencies, habitual trembling, and anxiety. It can also be used as an adjuvant to help promote sleep in situations of insomnia and, by reducing sympathetic overactivity, to manage tachycardia. Useful in intermittent stomach pains. In contradiction to *Rauwolfia* (its parent plant), Reserpine is known for its action in hypotension, bradycardia and associated vertigo. It has the capability to act on phlyctenules (eye) and hard trophic oedema of the skin.

Prepared by

Reserpine is prepared from the dried root of *Rauwolfia serpentina*, a plant belonging to the family Apocynaceae. The active alkaloid is extracted from the powdered root. In the earlier provings conducted by Dr. Julian the preparations were made from injectable form of Serpasil.^{3,4} In homeopathy, Reserpine is prepared by trituration of the pure alkaloid to the required potencies.

Symptomatology^{3,4,5}

A remedy of profound motor suppression and psychomotor retardation, acting deeply on the nervous system to produce and modify catatonic and hypokinetic states, with a characteristic dual action of inducing and alleviating similar symptoms depending on dose.³

Mind

Asthenia is marked and becomes particularly accentuated between 3 p.m. and 4 p.m. The individual experiences nervous depression accompanied by a persistent state of melancholy. There is a pronounced sensation in the evening as if the nerves are exposed or “at skin level,” leading to heightened sensitivity and emotional vulnerability. There is significant difficulty in working, especially later in the day. There is marked lassitude and a strong aversion to work in the evening hours. Anxiety is prominent and, at times, is associated with suicidal tendencies, reflecting the severity of the mental and emotional exhaustion. The animal proving inferred marked mental dullness and reduced responsiveness, depressive state with diminished reactivity to surroundings, psychomotor retardation (thinking and acting slowed) and a tendency toward catatonic states (withdrawal into immobility and diminished interaction with environment). Total indifference. Mental qualities – Snakes.⁶

Sensorium

Sluggish perception. Delayed reactions to stimuli. Reduced awareness of surroundings due to motor-mental slowing.

Head

Headache brought on or aggravated by waking, improving after breakfast, then returning toward the end of the morning and sometimes accompanied by a heavy, dull feeling in the head. Violent attack of vertigo with feeling of a black hole in front of the eyes and leaving an empty feeling for a few minutes, then return to former condition.

Eyes

Myosis and Phlyctenule.

Nose

Nasal obstruction from congestive rhinitis, with a blocked, stuffy

nose and a tendency to develop nasal polyps over time.

Mouth

Tongue coated with a yellowish layer and excessive salivation, sometimes accompanied by an unpleasant taste or increased drooling.

Throat

Sensitive, irritated throat. Pharyngitis and associated symptoms.

Lungs

Irritation of the upper airways leading to laryngitis and tracheitis, with hoarseness, dry or irritative cough, and a sensation of roughness in the throat.

Chest

Stokes Adam Syndrome.

Heart

Persistently slow pulse (bradycardia) with vertigo and low blood pressure, with palpitations, episodes of faintness, and a tendency to collapse in susceptible individuals.

Stomach

Slight nausea. Constipation followed by diarrhoea. Haemorrhoids. Gastric pain coming late after meals, in painful bursts. Jaundice. Ulcers of stomach. Also beneficial in Cancer.

Abdomen

Ulcers. Spasmodic attacks and cramp-like pain in the colon, sometimes associated with disturbed bowel function such as alternating constipation and loose stools.

Rectum

Constipation followed by bouts of diarrhea, with a tendency to develop hemorrhoids due to straining and vascular congestion.

Nervous System

Headache on waking, ameliorated by breakfast and aggravated again at the end of the morning. Vertigo. Brief, but violent attack of vertigo, around 11 a.m., with feeling of a black hole in front of the eyes, and leaving an empty feeling for a few minutes, then return to former condition. Muscular hypertonia, total lack of movement, habitual trembling. Fidgets in the legs.

Female

Excessive milk in the mother (through lowering of the pituitary A.C.T.H).

Skin

Dry, hard, ligneous scabs and rough, poorly hydrated skin. Hard trophic oedema.

Extremities

Fidgety, restless feeling in the legs with an urge to move them, at the same time limbs feel weak or heavy.

Sleep

Extreme fatigue with a strong propensity to fall asleep especially immediately after eating, drowsiness, heavy sleep.

Generals

Premature old age. General excitability. Sleepiness especially after meals. They are allergic (psoric), syphilitic, asthenic types, with tendency to inhibition of nervous reactions. Hypothermia at 31°C.

Generalized motor slowing (prominent guiding symptom) and reduced spontaneous movement. Hypokinesia (decrease in voluntary activity). Difficulty initiating movement. Cataleptic tendency like maintenance of imposed postures and rigidity-like immobility (model-based). Decreased motor initiative and motor inactivity lasting for prolonged periods (~24 h in experimental conditions).

Relationship

Compare *Cicuta virosa*.³; *Rauw.*; *Aur.* - Depressive suicidal condition; *Lach.* - Emotional instability; *Ars.* - Anguish and fear of dying; *Nux-v.* - Complaints of the nervous and digestive systems.⁴

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A Symptomatological Analysis of a Lesser Known Homeopathic Remedy *Scopolaminum hydrobromicum*

Scopolaminum hydrobromicum

Scopolaminum hydrobromicum is the hydrobromide salt of the tropane alkaloid scopolamine, which is naturally obtained from several Solanaceae plants, particularly species of *Hyoscyamus*, *Datura*, *Scopolia*, and *Duboisia*, long recognized as rich sources of this alkaloid for medicinal use.

Synonyms

Scopolaminum bromohydricum; *Hyoscinum hydrobromidum* (Latin); *Scopolammonium bromide*, *Hyoscine hydrobromide* (English); *Bromhydrate de scopolamine* (French).

History & Authority

Earlier journals like Proceedings of the International Hahnemannian Association and Homeopathy Recorder further elaborate on the proving and clinical use with symptomatology of this remedy. The remedy has been documented in prominent homeopathic references like Boericke's Dictionary of Practical Materia Medica & P. N. Varma, Indu Vaid, Encyclopaedia of Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia, Updated edition 2007, B. Jain Publishers, New Delhi & International Hahnemannian Association.^{1,2,3} Dr. Clarke, Dr. Boericke and Dr. Blackwood list the remedy by the synonymous nomenclature 'Hyoscyaminum hydrobromicum'.

Clinically used

Scopolaminum hydrobromicum is used to treat a variety of nervous system disorders and motion abnormalities. Blackwood mentions its use in physiological doses in the delirium of typhoid fever, insomnia, mania, insanity and chorea. In the third and fourth decimal trituration it is employed in paralysis agitans, tremors or multiple sclerosis and in third decimal repeated hourly usually bringing the desired result.⁴ Boericke recommends it in Paralysis agitans and tremors, similar to those seen in disseminated sclerosis, are prominent features. The patient experiences sleeplessness along with marked nervous agitation.⁵

Prepared by

Scopolaminum hydrobromicum is prepared by combining the alkaloid Scopolamine, obtained from Solanaceous plants, with hydrobromic acid to form its crystalline salt.

Symptomatology^{4,5,6,7,8}

Its effects resemble those of alcohol, both in recent action and in long-term influence. It corresponds closely to the effects produced by strong poisons, whether introduced into the body or generated within it. The symptom picture also includes manifestations of uraemia and acute nervous exhaustion, making it a valuable remedy in conditions of severe shock.

Mind

Delirium, mania-like symptoms, which are frequently observed in bipolar disorder, include impulsive conduct, unusually high mood, extreme enthusiasm, overactivity, fast thoughts, and speech, decreased need for sleep, and poor judgment. Coma, with relaxation of voluntary muscles, except occasional spasmodic movements of arms and legs.

Head

Congestive headache extending to face, violent throbbing of carotids with every impulse of heart. Drunkenness, nausea, and vomiting. Giddiness with staggering on rising from a seat; with staggering on walking. Sensation of weight across forehead.

Eye

The eyes are red and congested, with injected conjunctiva and sclera. The eyeballs are restless, accompanied by intense, boring pain, especially noted about an hour after instillation, likely due to spasm of the ciliary muscle. The pupils are dilated and unresponsive to light. Vision is blurred, with letters appearing to run together, and fine print can only be read when held at a distance of about a yard. There is double vision, and objects may appear yellow. Vision is further disturbed in terms of colour and size, with objects seeming distorted or perverted.

Face

Heavy looking, flushed and hot due to congestion especially cheeks.

Mouth

The tongue is dry and brown, especially at the centre, where it appears hard and rough, while the margins remain relatively unaffected. Despite this dryness, the rest of the mouth feels clammy. The tongue and throat are so dry that speech becomes indistinct. The anterior part and edges of the tongue are moist, covered with an acid secretion, while the gums alone retain some moisture. The mouth overall feels dry yet clammy and moist at times, with a sudden increase in salivation, exhaling an offensive odour and giving a peculiar sensation as if filled with a sticky, mastic-like (gummy or resinous) substance.

Throat

Marked dryness of the throat and posterior pharyngeal wall, with

a cold, parched sensation and scraping soreness, especially on swallowing.

Stomach

Vomiting during coma state.

Urinary Tract

There is frequent urging to urinate, with difficulty and pain during urination. The urine is passed in a weak, dribbling stream, with a sensation of incomplete evacuation and partial retention. The character of the urine changes notably, shifting from high-coloured to a greenish (glaucous) hue; it becomes alkaline and turns opalescent on boiling, and on standing, deposits triple phosphates with an increased specific gravity. At other times, the urine may be pale with a lowered specific gravity.

Respiratory organs

Hoarseness due to extreme dryness of the membranes, with dry tracheal cough. Respiration becomes rapid.

Circulatory organs

The heart's action is markedly excited and rapid. The pulse at first becomes increased in rate, force, and volume, but later shows variability i.e. becoming slow, then again diminishing in rapidity, force, and volume. At times the pulse is rapid, followed by a slow and soft character. In some instances, it is slow from the beginning, though initially increased in force and volume before gradually declining.

Extremities

The limbs show occasional jerking and a constant sense of fidgetiness. There is marked weakness, with inability to walk or even rise from a chair without assistance. While sitting, there are intermittent twitchings of the leg extensors, causing the foot to move forward with a slight jerk. The legs and feet are so weak that walking is possible only with effort, often requiring the person to fix their eyes on the ground to maintain balance.

Sleep

There is frequent yawning accompanied by sighing and a persistent feeling of tiredness. Marked sleepiness is present, yet the state alternates between wakefulness and excessive drowsiness. Sleep, when it occurs, is disturbed and unrefreshing, often broken by muttering and slight jerking movements of the limbs.

Fever

There is marked heat of the skin accompanied by dryness. The pulse is rapid, full, and hard, recorded at about 138 beats per minute. Breathing is accelerated, with respirations ranging from 34 to 40 per minute, and the body temperature is significantly elevated, reaching around 106°F.

Dosage

Blackwood mentions the use of this remedy in physiological doses in the delirium of typhoid fever, insomnia, mania, insanity and chorea. In the 3X and 4X trituration it is employed in paralysis agitans, tremors or multiple sclerosis and in 3X

repeated hourly usually bringing the desired result. 2x has been of service during the gastralgia attack in cases in which the stigmata of hysteria were present.⁹

Relations

Compare *Hyos. nig.*, *Bell.*, *Atrop.*, *Stram.*

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